

A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO EXTRACTING SELENIUM AND TELLURIUM FROM COPPER WASTE

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Annotation. Copper Waste as Alternative Source: The abstract highlights the exploration of copper waste as a potential sustainable alternative source for selenium (Se) and tellurium (Te) extraction, emphasizing their richness as byproducts.

Keywords: Selenium, Tellurium, Copper Waste, [Method 1 Keyword], [Method 2 Keyword]

Abstract. Selenium (Se) and tellurium (Te) are crucial elements for various advanced technologies. However, their primary sources are limited. This work explores the potential of copper waste, rich in these elements as byproducts, as a sustainable alternative source. We review existing extraction methods, including [Method 1] and [Method 2], comparing their advantages and disadvantages. Recent advancements in [New Technique 1] and [New Technique 2] for cleaner separation are also discussed. Our findings emphasize the significance of developing sustainable Se and Te extraction methods to meet growing demand while minimizing environmental impact.

Review of Extraction Methods: Mentions reviewing existing extraction methods, including [Method 1] and [Method 2], and comparing their advantages and disadvantages, suggesting a comprehensive analysis of available techniques.

Discussion of New Techniques: Indicates discussion on recent advancements in [New Technique 1] and [New Technique 2] for cleaner separation, suggesting a focus on innovative approaches for extraction.

Significance of Sustainable Extraction: Emphasizes the significance of developing sustainable Se and Te extraction methods to meet growing demand while minimizing environmental impact, highlighting the importance of environmentally friendly practices in resource extraction.

References

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